

The Importance of Textiles Hand in Comfort and Emotional Design

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to verify and evaluate the variable emotional response in interacting with a well-defined matter, fabrics, through different sensorial channels in order to allow designers to set or select textile parameters according to the emotion they would like to evoke in a specific sensorial condition.

The purpose is to create a universal and scientifically-based culture and language as a core for a quality control system of two fundamental elements: “hand” and comfort.

The research concerned several aspects of sensorial experience of textiles through the selection of the most influential sensations in textile applications and their relative possible correlation to mechanical properties. A group of subjects in different sensorial modalities was utilized in order to analyse transfer and anticipation phenomena.

Interesting deductions have been drawn by comparing objective parameters and correlated subjective sensations thereby opening up the potential to design emotional experience of textiles.

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Introduction and background

Emotions and the faculty of generating them through sensory stimulation represents the main feature that distinguishes humans from the inanimate world and, perhaps, from the remainder of living organisms too. In fact, anything interacting with our sensory organs affects our mood and way of living in such a remarkable way that modelling everyday objects represents a considerable responsibility on the part of designers for individual wellbeing.

Human life and experiences develop through a continuous relationship between inputs from outer contexts and outputs reacting to them, not only by promoting actions but also by affecting emotions.

Hence the shared belief in the necessity of a systematic study of the relationship between objects, sensations and emotions.

For a few years the research group has focused above all on the emotional value of a well-defined, common material: fabric. This may be defined as the result of weaving or knitting different kinds of yarns in various ways. Textiles are currently utilized in several industrial fields, including - most importantly - clothes and home dowry, but also in packaging, covers, upholstery and filters.

Historically, the main application of textiles, that is, the realization of clothing, implies the creation of products able to cover, protect and insulate human body from both atmospheric events and wounds, thus incrementing quality of life and comfort.

Continuous protection from external agents is actually able to evoke sensations of physical and psychological wellbeing, so that the study of the optimization of fabric functionality presents features influencing the condition of wellbeing. Mechanical, moisture and heat properties of fabrics have usually been studied with the aim of optimization, while less rigorous investigations have been carried out on the properties related to pleasure, or rather on the ways in which (textiles) objects may render their use pleasurable (Jordan, Green, 2002).

Pleasure in use is interpreted by many people as a twofold need. On one side there is the need for the practical use of the object itself and on the other side the user's need for emotional involvement and his / her desires in relation to the product. This refers to features influencing the user's psychological and emotional sphere.

Therefore, the aim of this research on pleasure is to evaluate subjective components of interaction, i.e. the value the user assigns to contact with products, and its translation into tools for design.

The research group has been dealing with the development of earlier tools for designing sensoriality, such as the atlas for the emotional and sensorial characterization of materials and their surfaces (Rognoli, Levi, 2004). The research focus is now moving towards the

investigation of the emotional contribution of a particular material, in this case textiles, and the General Atlas redirecting towards it.

Lastly, it should be mentioned that this research forms part of a broader study on comfort which investigates the contribution of textiles to this strategic and important field of the clothing industry.

Studies on hand

Sensoriality, usually called “hand” or “handle” in relation to fabrics, has been a research topic since the beginning of the last century. Among spontaneous and informal approaches to sensoriality, Annie Albers carried out in depth, brilliant research on the expressivity of fabrics during textiles design courses in Bauhaus (Disegno Industriale, 2006)

The first rationally supported surveys may be attributed to Binns and Peirce (Bishop, 1996, Peirce, 1930). However the first systematic approaches useful to factories date back to 1970 with Kawabata and Niwa, who attempted to develop appropriate methods to identify the ideal fabric for clothing applications according to subject and season on the basis of physical and mechanical properties (Kawabata et al., 2002).

High costs and limited verified correlations of the Kawabata Evaluation System for Fabric (KESF) stimulated further research on the topic, employing the correlation method between subjective sensations and emotions generated by fabrics and objective properties obtained through tests on the fabric itself.

This category of study lacks standard procedures, while the adoption of successful approaches from different fields, such as food or cosmetics, has proved inaccurate and even detrimental to identifying and elaborating sensations provoked by matter in the user.

Hence the intention of developing an easy way of studying and predicting sensoriality of textiles, especially in relation to the specific senses involved.

Sensorial ducts

Sensorial assessment of fabrics occurs through two main ducts: sight and touch.

The former is defined as the sense of distance and it is usually adopted in first phase of evaluation, for example a first response to a fabric displayed in a shop window. Visual evaluation often implies phenomena such as synaesthesia and processes of sensorial prediction, supplementing the work of other sensorial qualities typically connected to touch - like heaviness, warmth and softness - and thus enriching the perceptual frame with a mental image. Touch, instead, is the sense of closeness and contact. It has occupied a supporting role compared to sight in human history. Still, it appears to influence sensorial characterization of textiles and

the potential for emotion and comfort very deeply. It supplies detailed information about softness and smoothness, which are the two main qualities defining 'handle' (Bishop, 1996). Touch represents the broadest and most versatile sensorial duct of human body, owing to its location in the skin (about 18% of total human weight). Some consider it the most important human apparatus (Montagu, 1971).

According to the scope and modality of contact, skin sensitivity may be divided into the following categories:

- thermal
- tactile
- haptic

The first two modalities are related to sensations connected to detection of the position of objects near the organism. They imply a sort of indefinite and impalpable pleasure usually perceived during extended contact, thus influencing textiles 'handle'.

Haptic modality, instead, implies active involvement operations, usually but not necessarily sudden, in the form of gestures and operations such as catching, clasping, stretching and feeling. Haptic handling represents the most frequent modality of perception in the field of textiles, since it provides the most influential sensorial information.

During perception interactions between the two sensorial ducts (sight and touch) occur, thus giving rise to inter-sensorial modalities and transfer phenomena, that is different typologies of sensation which are reciprocally influential.

Very few studies deal with this subject, but among them Lederman's research (often and most recently with Klaztky) on transfer between sight and touch is perhaps most important (Lederman et al. 1986).

Objective and method

This research aims to detect and verify the correlation between sensorial feedback and physical and mechanical properties of fabric samples with varied composition and configuration.

The research intends to identify how the emotional aspect of textiles may be connected to properties such as softness or roughness, and the way they could affect human sensations and perceptions.

All design fields share the intention of determining the grammar and the syntax of a language which characterizes matter and surfaces which interact with our sensoriality, thus exciting deep-rooted aspects of our own intellectual, emotional and sensorial reactivity.

The potential identification of handle parameters would imply very useful benefits in the world of textiles, making it possible to predict sensoriality of fabrics in a systematic and sharable way through values obtained by set processes and well-defined translational modalities. Then both users and professionals may easily communicate and understand each other, avoiding doubts and mistakes, thus accelerating communication and optimizing quality of comprehension.

On the basis of sensation predictability, designing sensoriality for well-defined users becomes possible, as well as communicating the idea to professional figures involved at several levels and for different motives, such as the supplier, stylist and user.

Nowadays, “handle” assessment is characterized by an empirical approach among experts in industrial activities, who carry out an evaluation process consisting of feeling fabric samples with the hands and making a personal judgment about the sensations fabrics infuse in their subjective mood. A universally shared system of comparison does not exist yet although it appears necessary in the field of design, which is based on the importance of the emotional aspect of materials.

Kobayashi classified handle research into 8 categories, according to the aim and the modality of evaluation (Kobayashi, 1968). Our research approach appears to belong to the third category, including statistical analyses on the relationship between sensory grading and physical characteristics. The research shares some elements and principles in common with other approaches. This was necessary in order to conduct the studies and experiments, above all in relation to test modalities and interpretation of information.

Method

Experiments involved three different groups of homogeneous subjects, all of whom were required to express their sensations and the emotions induced by a selection of 7 fabric samples, perceived in threefold sensorial modalities.

First, it was necessary to identify the sensorial properties of each fabric which were believed to be most influential to the user’s perception. According to previous literature and our own experts’ opinions, selected properties are:

- softness (stiff – soft axis)
- roughness (rough – smooth axis)
- warmth (cool – warm axis)

Then, we hypothesized the relationship between each sensation with objective properties such as:

- fiber

- weaving method
- physical and mechanical fabric properties

The selection of the first group of 20 fabrics followed crossed criteria, including a well-balanced selection taking into consideration both fiber (100% cotton or mixed) and processing (weaving or knitting).

The research continued with the evaluation of physical and mechanical properties. Parameters considered influential in fabric sensoriality are: stiffness, strength, thickness and specific heat. Each parameter was measured through appropriate instruments and the resulting data were analyzed and elaborated according to manifold points of view, by performing the same test on a specific property in different ways or by extrapolating several data from a single test.

Sample selection

On the basis of the objective ranking of the first group of 20 samples, we selected a smaller group of 7 fabrics to facilitate sensorial assessment and the realization of the subjective ranking. In fact, previous research demonstrated that the use of a number of more than 10-12 samples brought subjects to a state of uncertainty and unreliability, while a number of 7-8 samples was found to be the optimal value. The selection included samples distributed evenly throughout the different kinds of mechanical scales, including extreme and central positions, to obtain a varied although small sample group. At the same time, the selection incorporated the presence of fibers and processing methods from across the spectrum of the world of textiles. The final sample group of 7 fabrics included 4 fabrics in 100% cotton and 3 in mixed fibers, and at the same time 4 woven fabrics and 3 knitted.

Figure 1: selection of 7 samples including 4 fabrics in 100% cotton (light blue) and 3 in mixed fibers (purple), and 4 woven fabrics (yellow) and 3 knitted (green).

Subjective evaluation

The 7 samples were then evaluated by 11 subjects, grouped according to their relation to and experience with matter. The groups are:

- Textile Expert (ET), a professional figure in materials research for the clothing field.
- Materials Expert (EM), professional figures connected with the evaluation of either mechanical or sensorial properties of the matter in general.
- Control Group (GC), common figures unrelated to the study of the matter, but homogeneous in age and provenance.

The involvement of different groups aimed to detect possible traces of either manifold or univocal approaches to subjective sensoriality. Subjects who are familiar with textile matter were selected in order to study the influence of technical knowledge on perceptive experience. Each subject was requested to rank the samples in decreasing order according to each sensorial property (softness, roughness, warmth). This evaluation was repeated in three perceptual modalities - mono-sensorially (firstly only sight, and then only touch), and finally multi-sensorially - with an interval of 10 minutes between each evaluation to avoid transfer of phenomena, both positive and negative.

In the first sensorial evaluation phase involving only sight, samples were arranged side by side, opposite the subject at a distance of 50 centimeters and without tactile contact. This evaluation required a notable investment of time by subjects before they were able to express their own sensations and emotions, highlighting the importance of touch in fabric perception.

The second (haptic) phase involving only touch required “blind” subjects, totally autonomous in the manipulation and arrangement of samples. In this phase each subject employed well-characterized gestures that Lederman would call Exploratory Procedures (EP) (Lederman, Klatzky, 1993).

Finally, the multi-sensorial approach involved both visual and tactile organs through a crossed and simultaneous evaluative assessment of textile sensoriality. Subjects appeared to be more resolved in the translation of their emotions into rankings.

Perception gestures

Observation of the subjects’ approaches permitted the detection of the modalities through which users interacted with the matter, usually by employing gestures which were deeply rooted in the memory and referred specifically to the defined property to be analysed.

The first visual modality restricted subject interaction to only direct sight. At times subjects moved closer, further away or around to change their point of view with respect to the static sample.

In this phase subjects made reference above all to the drapery of the fabric; how the fabric wrinkled on itself or on the supporting plane. They also focused their attention on the ratio between lighted and shaded macro (creases) and micro (roughness) areas.

The second phase, the haptic assessment, presented the most variable approaches. Many subjects employed unusual gestures to overcome the absence of the contribution made by sight. Manipulation became slower, probably with the intention of visualizing in the mind the superficial properties detected by the skin.

Generally, subjects tended to clasp and scrunch up the piece of fabric to evaluate the softness, thus compressing the volume of the sample.

With the purpose of assessing the warmth, instead, subjects tended to put their hands above the fabric for few seconds, usually without moving them, and often compared pairs of samples simultaneously. Some subjects, especially female, preferred to draw the fabric samples up to their cheeks, assumed more sensitive to warmth perception.

Finally, evaluation of texture was based on ‘scratching’ the fabric in manifold ways, for example by sliding either the fingertips on the fabric faces or the whole palm over the flat sample on the plane, or by wrapping the fabric around the hand.

The multi-sensorial assessment phase appeared faster than the other two, probably because of the simultaneous elaboration of multiple stimuli and information deriving from different apparatus or perhaps because of the memory of previous sensations. Therefore subjects adopted the same approaches described previously but with an accelerated rhythm and a faster response, thus expressing a higher degree of self-confidence in the translation of stimuli provided by the fabric into the emotion evoked.

Figures 2: example of touching gestures in assessment of warmth.

Figures 3-4: examples of haptic gestures in assessment of softness.

Figures 5-6: examples of touching gestures in assessment of warmth and roughness.

Check system of sensorial forecasting

The most important purpose of this research is to develop a system of textiles sensorial forecasting based on objective fundamentals which can be used to predict the affinity of users with particular textiles. With reference to what has been previously stated in this paper, and using the subjective and objective rankings realized during the tests, a system which permits the interpretation of data collected and the verification of the correspondence between a sensation and the respective property involved has been defined. The result is a matrix which can verify if an affinity exists between a mechanical property and a sensation, and thus a capacity of prediction which is not general but may be used to anticipate whether a given property effectively anticipates a sensation.

The comparison matrix (see example in Table 1, softness ranks) is made up of the subjective rank (reference) and objective rank (to be valued). It's organized in 7 columns (number of samples) and in 3 lines. The first line is the sensorial and subjective rank, the second is the objective rank obtained by tools of measurement. Both subjective and objective records were arranged into decreasing ranks and compared with each other.

The third line quotes the objective rank score of each sample; the score is obtained by calculating the shift (difference) from its position on the subjective rank.

It's possible to get the total with a series of calculations that have to take into account a multiplicative factor variable according to the position of a textile in the objective rank; lower in the middle and increasing towards the extremes.

The higher the number, the greater the affinity between subjective and objective ranks. The maximum value is 7 and the affinity is considered good until -3.

value	x4	x3	x2	x1	x2	x3	x4
subjective ranking	2	23	21	9	4	8	28
objective	2	21	9	23	4	28	8
shifted positions	0	2	1	1	0	1	1
total	-9						

Table 1: evaluation matrix.

General prediction ability

Graphs 1-2-3 represent a general analysis of all the collected data. They incorporate the prediction potential with respect to a defined perceptual property (row of monochromatic spheres) grouped on the basis of the sense involved (3 distinct graphs) and also of subjective groups typology (acronym).

The graphs provide qualitative information about firstly the degree of affinity of the parameter adopted for the comparison to the subjective rank (corresponding sphere position on the y-axis – appreciated for values above 0), and secondly the variability of comparing data with each group subject, that is the variance (sphere size).

Graphs 1-2-3: general affinity between a sensation and the associated objective parameter.

In these graphs, softness predictability (yellow spheres) is represented on the basis of the initial modulus parameter combined with thickness. Warmth ranking (pink spheres) is elaborated on

the basis of specific heat, and roughness (light blue spheres) is connected to a medium friction coefficient.

According to this graph and thus to the correspondences hypothesized:

- The objective parameter adopted for softness presents an impressive potential for prediction uniformly among the different subjects groups and senses. Sight (dark green graph) is a small exception.
- The warmth parameter demonstrates very negative and variable parameters, as highlighted by the variance, but with an increasing affinity following involvement of touch (light green graph)
- The roughness parameter is highly variable in relation to both sensorial modality and the group involved, with a moderate level of variance.

Therefore, on one hand softness is a highly predictable property even in this general analytical phase. On the other hand the two remaining sensorial properties will require a more detailed analysis based on objective parameters and ungrouped subjects in order to avoid high levels of variance and variability.

Sensoriality ratio

Very interesting qualitative deductions may be drawn from the crossed comparison between multi-sensorial and mono-sensorial rankings. The application of the evaluation method previously adopted shows the mono-sensorial modality influencing to the largest extent the multi-sensorial perception of the same sensorial property.

As presented by graph 4, warmth and roughness multi-sensorial perceptions appear similar to the corresponding mono-sensorial ones both in terms of affinity and the number of subjects most guided by sight or touch.

Focusing on each perceptual property, subjects revealed a partly shared difficulty, for example, in the distinction between fabrics which felt warmer rather than cooler. Subjects familiar with textile matter also usually tended to connect visual warmth impressions especially to the method of processing the fabric; knitted textiles were classified as warmer than woven ones. Within this tendency, it was sometimes evident that expert subjects usually considered 100% cotton fabrics warmer if knitted but cooler if woven in comparison with mixed fibers samples.

An analogous phenomenon of connection between textile sensation and processing methods occurred in the arrangement of the roughness ranking. Some subjects tended to relate a sandy sensation to the woven fabrics, while the knitted ones were perceived as smoother, especially in the assessment process supported by sight.

Graph 4: graph representing sensoriality ratio. The dimension of the sphere indicates the number of subjects who were most guided by the organ under consideration compared with multi-sensorial perception.

Softness perception is decidedly different, since the two senses of sight and touch contributed in a dissimilar manner to multi-sensorial perception. Touch appeared to be the most influential parameter in the multi-sensorial approach considering the number of subjects guided by it, but excellent values for affinity were also noted in the case of subjects mostly guided by sight. In this latter case, the identification of common features in subjects with evident multi-sensorial anticipation just by sight suggests that the softness of textiles, clothes, upholsteries softness can be communicated successfully with a high degree of reliability through visual media. Visual communication represents an enormous potential above all for distance communication, maintaining a low risk of misunderstanding and accelerating the whole communication process.

General deductions and outlooks

Feeling as a common and shared experience

According to our research, often supported by previous studies, the sample groups involved demonstrated similar approaches to perception of textiles. This is probably justified by the commonality of sensorial experience in general, without the necessity of technical competence and knowledge of the correct sensorial translation.

Touching as roughness average calculus

Perception of roughness through touch appeared particularly predictable both for qualitative values and in relation to the number of subjects guided by this sense, above all in multi-sensorial perception characterized by a high value of affinity.

The medium friction coefficient rather than the front or back surfaces emerged as the optimal parameter, as if the brain or the cerebral cortex made a mathematical calculation of incoming stimuli from manifold organs simultaneously or in different moments, unifying them in an average value.

See the softness warmth

Warmth perception is highly variable, but many subjects associated it to fabric softness, above all in the sight only evaluation. In fact, specific heat combined with the initial modulus predicted warmth perception in more than 25% of subjects. Remaining sensations are less accurately but not badly predicted by this parameter.

Softness as a predictable and shared sensation

Softness through touch appeared as a highly predictable and shared property of textiles, as confirmed by the low variance value.

The parameter that almost flawlessly provides an excellent predictor of sensoriality is the initial modulus (that is the rigidity measured in the first phase of textile elongation due to the yarns pattern stretching) combined with thickness. These deductions open up wide and novel design scenarios, above all in communication and design of softness.

Softness label and symbol

Predictability of softness perception presents a great potential in both general and clothing design fields. Thanks to readily available and applicable tests, this evaluation method assures accurate sensorial prediction and it can be assumed as a parameter for comparison in relation to design hypothesis and constraints typical of the early conceptual phase. Here, a sensorial threshold value may be fixed according to the desired softness and application, leading to a systematic and accurate approach for emotional design, above all in the case of a wide choice.

This method avoids subjective contrasting opinions about fabrics “handle”, as nowadays happens, especially for ordinary textiles selection.

Conclusions

With the consolidated aim of developing useful and efficient tools to evaluate emotional load of matter in the design field, the research group focused attention on the predictability of sensations and emotions evoked by textiles by comparing subjective and objective rankings. With reference to previous studies, we connected and compared well-defined physical and mechanical parameters to specific sensations and were able to deduce very interesting potential correlations. Ability to predict softness was found to be extremely reliable, therefore a further investigation and a more profound study of this sensation in particular is scheduled as part of the development of an efficient and universal instrument able to communicate sensorial and emotional feedback predictions.

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